

Co-medication of insulin and metformin in type 1 (LADA) diabetes

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Abstract

Type 1 diabetes (autoimmune, T1D), including the latent autoimmune diabetes in adults (LADA) variant, is managed by injecting insulin to a target glycaemic range. Co-medication with metformin is not common but might reduce hepatic glycogenolysis and insulin resistance, thus improving glucose control with a reduced insulin dosage.

Reduced insulin use is associated with reduced risk for hypoglycaemia and weight gain, as well as being less expensive.

In this case report, 500mg of metformin daily showed a marked reduction of insulin requirement by about 10 IU per day. However, it produced no clear evidence of reduced mid-morning glucose peak. Published trials suggest a similar reduction in insulin requirement, but using 1000-2000 mg metformin per day.

Co-medication of low dose metformin reduced the total daily insulin requirement as effectively as higher doses.

Introduction

Metformin is commonly the first line of therapy on diagnosis of type 2 diabetes (T2D), while type 1 diabetics (T1D) are prescribed insulin treatment (Poretsky 2017). A subset of T1D is latent autoimmune diabetes in adults (LADA), often initially diagnosed as T2D. This features the presence of insulin resistance and a pronounced honeymoon period before insulin therapy is required (Tuomi et al. 1993, Buzzetti et al. 2017, Rocha et al. 2023).

Although metformin is not typically prescribed for T1D (Mayo Clinic n.d.), there have been a number of trials co-medicating metformin and standard insulin treatments for T1D conditions (Moon et al. 2007, Ansari et al. 2008, Vella et al. 2010, Liu et al. 2015, Nadeau et al. 2015, Livingstone et al. 2017, Beysel et al. 2018, Yan et al. 2023, Poh Shean et al. 2023). In almost all cases, they report a reduction in insulin requirement, although quite often the emphasis is more focused on a reduced glycaemic variability (daily range of glucose concentrations). Other targets such as weight loss, serum lipid content and systolic blood pressure were not consistently changed. Reduced insulin resistance through addition of metformin is sometimes considered the reason for a reduction in insulin requirement (Livingstone et al. 2017).

Case and therapy

A previous case report describes the treatment programme following initial T2D diagnosis. Subsequently the diagnosis was changed to LADA, with a focus on introducing a ketogenic diet (Nelson & Jacobs 2017). Insulin therapy was introduced in 2018 and subsequently resolved to Lantus alone as a single basal dose in the morning. The amount of insulin was self-monitored and titrated up or down as

evidenced by regular daily finger prick blood glucose concentrations. HbA_{1c} results, monitored initially 6 monthly and subsequently annually, indicated <58 mmol/mol and commonly in the 48-53 range. The New Zealand diabetic recommendation is to target below 60 mmol/mol (7.6%) (Diabetes Info NZ n.d.).

A ketogenic diet, described earlier, was continued and refined slightly to target a daily carbohydrate intake of less than 30g per day. Over the years, it was noted that the peak of the daily finger-prick glucose measurement was commonly mid-morning, around 9:30-10:00 a.m., even when fasting. This strongly indicates hepatic glycogenolysis. Metformin is reputed to inhibit hepatic glycogenolysis, (Viollet et al. 2012, Wu et al. 2017, LaMoia & Shulman 2021). Although metformin is not commonly associated with T1D patients, it was thought that the metformin action might reduce this mid-morning increase in glucose concentration (Adak et al. 2018, Vial et al. 2019).

Metformin therapy at 500mg with breakfast was begun in addition to the standard approach of Lantus basal injections. This dosage was chosen because prior therapy, at 1000mg per day, resulted in some unwanted effects, specifically minor gastric disturbance and alterations in sense of smell and taste (Nelson & Jacobs 2017, Nelson 2019).

Figure 1: Low dose 500mg daily metformin started 30th July 2023 (red diamond symbol). Six-times daily serum glucose concentrations (left hand axis) indicate a marked reduction in daily range with regular daily minimum close to a hypoglycaemic concentration. Daily insulin (IU, right hand axis) demonstrates a marked reduction in insulin required to prevent frank hypoglycaemia. The mid-morning readings are marked with a square symbol.

Result

No effect was noted until the third day, after which it became obvious that a marked reduction of insulin was required to prevent hypoglycaemia (Figure 1). Over the following weeks, this stabilised to ~10 units per day reduction. Note the initial difficulty in correctly titrating insulin requirement indicated by the sudden reduction and then variability in daily range over the following days. The brief increase in insulin demand is just prior to introducing metformin. This reflects the naive sudden decision to see what would happen by adding metformin rather than a particularly considered trial protocol which would exclude or delay initiating metformin until a more stable insulin regime has occurred.

The period indicated is too short to see the common weight loss effect of metformin (Nadeau et al. 2015) or long-term reduction in insulin use (The DCCT Research Group 1988, Purnell et al. 1998, Russell-Jones & Khan 2007). Previously observed unwanted effects of metformin therapy at 1000mg per day did not repeat at this reduced dose.

The primary assumed benefit of metformin to reduce the mid-morning glucose concentration peak is not clear or consistent (Figure 1). Monitoring over subsequent months has shown a continued variability in the peak glucose concentration with no clear indication of the supposed metformin effect, other than overall reduced insulin requirement.

Discussion

The near immediate response, after the ~3 day initiation period, to low dose metformin co-therapy was a steady reduction in insulin required over the first ~12 days, followed by reaching a new plateau. This represents a marked drop in insulin requirements and thus represents a considerable saving in costs, considering metformin is substantially cheaper than insulin. More importantly, reduced insulin need could well have beneficial effects on weight, with associated blood pressure and lipid benefits (Purnell et al. 1998, Russell-Jones & Khan 2007, Templeman et al. 2017).

Reported trials of metformin co-therapy in T1D used 500mg or 1000mg twice daily (1000-2000mg daily total). Metformin is known to cause some intestinal and other effects, but reducing the dose to only 500mg per day in this case prevented these other effects occurring, yet clearly retained a similar reduced total daily insulin requirement. Although some trials report a reduced daily glucose variability, this case report is unable to confirm this finding, but the reduced requirement for insulin is very clear.

Other glucose-lowering therapies alongside insulin in T1D have been the DPP-4 inhibitors (gliptins). These also demonstrate a reduced requirement for insulin with the added benefit of reducing the risk of hypoglycaemic events (Pinheiro et al. 2016, Yan et al. 2023). The metformin enhancement of insulin sensitivity, or reduction of insulin resistance, could be causing this effect (Pryor & Cabreiro 2015). Possibly a gut-mediated effect of metformin is one step to explaining an overall reduction in insulin requirement (Buse et al. 2015).

The lack of any clear signal of metformin limiting mid-morning glucose concentration daily peaks indicates this is not the driver for reduced insulin demand. Note the initial marked reduction in glucose concentration variability, but a subsequent return to the more normal range. Thus it seems unlikely that metformin, in this instance and from very limited data, is not associated with inhibition of hepatic glycogenolysis other than perhaps for a short period following initiation of this therapy (Figure 1).

The presence of insulin resistance is a feature of LADA (Tuomi et al. 1993). Insulin resistance is defined as a reduced ability of a specific quantity of insulin to reduce blood glucose concentration, while the many other actions of insulin are not affected (Lebovitz 2001). Hyperinsulinaemia, whether natural or through exogenous insulin, is needed to manage glucose and thus can result in other aspects of insulin activity continuing to produce components of metabolic syndrome, such as hypertension and lipid changes (Lebovitz 2001). Thus the potential for metformin to act as an insulin sensitising agent may provide other benefits associated with a reduction in hyperinsulinaemia.

Apart from glucose management, metformin also offers some other benefits. It has been demonstrated to provide some benefit in terms of cancer (DeCensi et al. 2010, Cerezo et al. 2013, Eikawa et al. 2015, Griss et al. 2015), although at considerably increased dosage than used here. In addition, there are indications of potential vascular disease reduction (Triggle et al. 2023) and as an anti-ageing therapy (Xenos et al. 2022).

Conclusion

The expected reduction in serum glucose concentrations, often an end point of metformin/insulin trials, is not a suitable end point as these medications are typically titrated to achieve a preferred glucose concentration target. In all reports and this case, insulin dosage needed to be adjusted downwards, in order to maintain the desired glucose range. The considerably lower metformin dose used here, compared with the doses used in published trials, appears to provide a similar reduction in insulin requirement.

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